

The Concept of Sect in the Interwar Period

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ABSTRACT: Due to the mechanisms of socialization, urbanization and globalization, the society resembles increasingly the structure of an intimate ecosystem. Therefore, when one approaches various subjects or, even more importantly, when one enunciates various concepts one must take into account their impact and significance at global level. As this paper analyses the use of the concept of “sect” during the interwar period, the author notes how the term had different connotations on each side of the Atlantic Ocean. On the Western side, the term “sect” had designated a state of affairs that emerged from the segregation of a group of believers from the mother–community of faith, and it is found used both as colloquialism as well as in academic settings. In Europe, however, the term “sect” acquired strong pejorative meaning, as the term was used with the intent to marginalize and stigmatize those labeled as such.

KEY WORDS: sect, State, Church, Neo–Protestant, interwar

Introduction

An analysis of the concept of “sect” in the interwar Romanian historiography can prove significant as it introduces a new dimension in the discussions regarding the history of the neo-protestant confessions. The undertaking is useful within the conceptual history, as “the conceptual history seeks the renewal of perspectives on a historical entity by assuming an alternative cultural paradigm, that is, by adopting political languages similar

to the advanced societies of the European Union.”¹ The study of history, as witness of the past, must be correlated also with the evolution of language, culture and political thinking, and not only with the account of events and facts or statistic data. When it comes to the history of the cultural-linguistic minorities and majorities, it is essential to overcome the parallel languages.² The language has changed in the course of the years and some of the terms have acquired new valences; at present, they can no longer define the same things as a century ago. Given all these, we will begin by looking at the sociological and theological meaning of the term; then we will analyze the way in which the concept of “sect” has been used in the state church language, in legislation and the news media; and, finally, we shall see what relevancy still holds today the usage of this term.

1) Sect: Sociological and Theological Perspectives

Etymologically, the term comes from the Latin *sequi*, meaning also “to follow a model, a person, an idea, a party etc.”³ The second etymology—erroneous, but more popular—comes from the Latin term *secare*, meaning “breaking up, segregation from the church.” From a theological point of view, beyond the etymological meaning of the term, the “sect” results from the segregation from a “mother church” or a larger community, separation triggered by a divergent understanding of the religious truth or a religious practice, different interpretation of the Scriptures etc. In the view of the mother-community, this schism constitutes an apostasy; in the view of the dissident community, it means a return to or a progress toward a better or purer faith. Thus, the “sect” involves theological and/or religious practice differences and schism or only schism, for which reason it will always stand in opposition with the mother-community with which it broke. Still, despite this opposition, the sect’s antithesis remains intimately connected with the mother-church’s thesis, be that Orthodox, Roman-catholic or Protestant. From a sociologically point of view, the “sect”, as form of religious organization, is defined, beginning with Max Weber and Ernst Troeltsch, in relation to and by comparison with the mother-church. While the latter is a religious

organization well-integrated in society, large-sized, impersonal and bureaucratized, with the majority of its members being born in it, the sect is a voluntary association that does not claim authority on the religious life and the conduit of the non-members and that stands in a tense relation with the overall society.⁴

In the Romanian historiography, the “sect” concept has not been approached save with a very few exceptions and usually and most often with an emphasis on emotional issues, statistical data, brief histories of diverse newly appeared confessions or with the purpose of upholding the idea of freedom of religion. All of these have played a major role in defining the “sects”, as well as the way in which the State and the society relate to them.

A real difficulty raised by the term “sect” is given by the fact that it has different purports, depending on which side of the Atlantic you are. Thus, in the United States, the term is understood strictly as a sociological concept, as it was used by Max Weber and Ernst Troeltsch. But, in the European colloquial language, “sect” has turned into a value judgment. Being used by the Christian churches in an apologetic and polemical way, to describe the heretical groups that segregate from the official Christianity, the term has acquired in the last century, a negative and derogatory connotation, thus losing its original meaning. In the colloquial language, the negative meaning of the term prevails, while the sociological meaning is totally ignored.

Across the centuries, religion has played an essential role in defining the identity of a society and its coagulation. The victory of liberalism in the modern times made this role appear obsolete, with religion being a matter of personal choice, indifferent to the State, as guaranteed by the 1923 Constitution, Article 22.⁵ Most often, this remained only a desideratum because, in reality, the State was never indifferent to religious matters, given the importance held by religion in the lives of its citizens. Also, the State couldn't afford to be indifferent to the social power yielded by religion, which was far from being weakened. It is important to note how “different religious cults were controlled in the name of the ‘police’ role that the State must assume, as harmonizer of the social environment and the public morality.”⁶ This way, it becomes justified that room for maneuver that the State ensures for itself in the existence of most European

constitutions, by stipulating that a cult is recognized as long as its ideas do not contradict “the public order and the morals and manners,”⁷ a concept with a broad sense that usually included those manifestations likely to lead to the destructuralization of the society.

Nonetheless, when the State was granted a more important role and the sense of lack of cohesion within the State was more acute, it can be noticed a permanent and active intervention of the state authorities within the cults, leading to the rediscovery in the modern era, of the political role that religion can play. Especially in Eastern Europe, this phenomenon was very intense. In the East, the case of Russia and the role played by Orthodoxy represents a notorious example; while in the West, we can note the importance of Catholicism in the life of the Habsburg Empire. The most interesting example remains the Bismarckian Germany, promoter of the *Kulturkampf* politics by which it was sought to counteract the Roman-Catholic Church and to increase the role of the Lutheran Church in the life of the State and the German society. There was a legacy of German Protestant traditions, of the *cuius region, eius religio* principle, valorized in the modern sense of the *raison d’État*.⁸

In this cultural environment, the modern definition of “sect” was penned by the German sociologist Ernst Troeltsch. According to Troeltsch, within the Christian religion, two utterly opposed forms of organization existed: the Church and the State. As Bryan Wilson underscores, “Troeltsch had in mind as a church model, the traditional churches as they looked in the national states of his time, and especially the ‘German Evangelical Church’, building the specificity of each as a series of dichotomous variables.”⁹ Although this pattern was built on the premise that the “perfect” model of church is that of the German national Protestant Church, Troeltsch thought to extend it also for the Catholic Church. From the Roman-catholic side objections were raised, especially by Werner Stark.

In the works of Troeltsch’s disciples, we find defined with more precision a series of “sects” characteristics, useful to be mentioned here:

1. The exclusivist character—by this it was understood the unacceptability of a double religious affiliation.
2. The claim of monopoly on the religious truth, in its totality.

3. The tendency to take on a secular profile due to its overall anti-sacerdotal character.
4. The rejection of any type of classification or division of the social body, on religious criteria, with the exception of the founders or the leaders, and that only in certain cases.
5. The voluntary character—each new “sect member” adheres freely and willingly to the respective religious group, often after having been submitted to verifications (tests) in order to be accepted.
6. The high moral standards maintained within the group.
7. The complete loyalty imposed to the adherent by the “sect”, with membership becoming the most important identity element, at the expense of the national loyalty, for instance.
8. The character of dissenting group—whereas in the Middle Ages and at the beginning of the modern era, the protest was aimed at the Church, its teachings and its priests, as we approach the present times, the protest turns against the increasingly secularized society, the “sect” defining most often a purpose, an objective surpassing the common morality, often imposed by the State, but manifested in gestures, attitudes that could contradict what was promoted by the State.¹⁰

It can be noted that although an objective analysis of the sectarian phenomenon is attempted, there is in these definitions, in a latent state, a strong deprecatory shade that will evolve with time, charging this idea of “sect” with negative connotations.¹¹ According to a recent definition by Peter Berger, “a sect is a religious small group, existing in a state of permanent tension with the entire society, impervious to its influence, and demanding from its members total fidelity and solidarity.”¹²

Thus, the “sect” is the ferment of a crisis, of a rupture within the society, if not through an attack against the “morals and manners”, at least by separating itself from the rest of the community and by questioning the existent social institutions. Also, the “sect” is the enemy of the institutionalized or State-subservient religions (after the Constantine model) by virtue of the new teachings it propagates

and the often aggressive proselytism aimed, at least in the initial phase, against the group from which it segregated. Sometimes, the “sect” becomes the adversary of the State by the segregation and fragmentation it initiates, by its detachment toward the State’s commandments, and such acts could only displease an increasingly authoritarian State.¹³

In conclusion, the “sect” defines a religious and social category comprising the new religious groups that do not stand yet in harmony with the rest of society and the State (for some, this intermediary state could last for centuries). Frequently, in order to acquire a legal status, these sects will have to go through a legislative “purgatory” set up by the State, with the purpose of convincing the State that they don’t pose any threat to it, and the “sects” will endeavor to assure the State by various manifestations that they are loyal to the established order. Nonetheless, there will be cases in which the “sects” will refuse to adapt or the State will do everything to place in the “sect” category, various cults that are incommensurable to its authority.

2) The Concept of “sect” as Used by the Ministry of Cults and Arts in the Interwar Period and During the Antonescu Regime

The official recognition of the Adventist and Baptist confessions came with the Ministerial Decision no. 32950/June 1921,¹⁴ signed by the Minister Octavian Goga and comprising three points. The first point specified that “the exercise of the Baptist Cult and the Adventist Cult is free.” For these cults to be free, the second point of the decision stipulated that “the propaganda will avoid denigrating the existent churches and the ecclesiastical personnel.” Afterwards, these two neo-protestant confessions will be recognized through repeated ministerial decisions. In 1933, the Plymouth Brethren confession was recognized through the ministerial decision no. 114119/August 21, 1933.

In the official acts issued by the Ministry of Cults in the interwar period, there can be noted the avoidance of using the “sect” terminology for both the recognized and the illegal cults. The ministerial decision no. 5735/January 29, 1925, Article 1, reads as

follows: “There are utterly forbidden the following associations of religious character (religious sects): (1) The Nazarenes (the penitents); the International Association of the Bible Students (the Millenists); (3) the Reformed Adventists; (4) the Reapers; (5) the Pentecostals; (6) The Inochentists, due to the fact that the doctrines they propagate contravene to the State’s Laws and institutions and by virtue of their practices they go against the public order.”¹⁵ Article 2 stated that “The Baptist and the Seventh-day Adventist associations continue to enjoy the rights and freedoms granted by the Constitution to associations, in general.”

It can be noted the tendency of the Ministry of Cults to avoid the usage of the term “sect”, this term being used only within brackets and for explicatory purposes for the general public—as in the case of the designations appearing next to some religious associations. In all ministerial decisions issued in the interwar period, the State avoided to use the term “sect” with reference to some cults or religious associations already recognized. Nonetheless, we can discern a duplicitous character when it comes to secret circular orders sent to prefects or constabularies, in which the term “sect” is used for some confessions already recognized.

The term “sect” doesn’t appear at all in the text of the Ministerial Decision no. 114119/1933, issued by the Ministry of Cults. The first article of this decision stated that “it is utterly forbidden the activity of the following religious associations: The International Association of the Bible Students, the Millenists, the Jehovah’s Witnesses (or the Witnesses of God—Jehovah), the Pentecostals, the Apostolic Church of God, the Nazarenes, the Inochentists, the Adventists—Reformed and Reapers, due to the fact that their doctrines contravene to the State’s Laws and institutions, and by virtue of their practices they go against the public order and morality.”¹⁶ The second article announced the recognition of a new religious confession, along with the Adventist and Baptist confessions: “The rights and freedoms granted by the Constitution to associations, in general, will be enjoyed by the religious associations of the Seventh-day Adventists, the Baptists and the Plymouth Brethren.”¹⁷

The idea of “sect” begins to be overtly used by the Ministry of the National Culture and Cults, during the dictatorship of Marshal

Antonescu, as we can see in the decree by which Antonescu took away the official status of all neo-protestant religious associations that had been recognized by the State, in the interwar period. The second article of this decree specified that “the existent religious associations (sects), *de iure* and *de facto*, are and remain abolished.”¹⁸ In the report presented by the Minister of National Culture and Cults to Marshal Antonescu and which form the basis for the decree from December 28, 1942, we can see a change in language, as the idea of “sect” is used profusely in connection with the up-till-then recognized religious associations, as well as with those religious associations not yet recognized. The idea of “sect” will be profusely used during the Antonescu period, in reference to the previously recognized Neo-protestant cults.¹⁹

3) The Concept of “Sect” in the Orthodox Discourse

Grigore Comşa,²⁰ Bishop of Arad, was an emblematic personality given the offices he had occupied in the Ministry of Cults and Arts, after the Great Union (Secretary, Vice-director, then General Vice-director between 1920 and 1925 at the Ministry of Cults and Arts in Bucharest), and his “anti-sectarian” writings. By reading his works, one can discern his preference for the term “sect” over the phrase “religious association” that the Ministry of Cults and Arts was using for the recognized neo-protestant confessions. We mention here some of the books he published and in which he used profusely the term “sect” in connection with some State-recognized religious associations and confessions: *Călăuza cunoaşterii şi combaterii sectelor*,²¹ *Pentru neam şi lege*,²² *Baptismul din punct de vedere istoric, naţional şi religios*,²³ *Cenuşa de pe capul bapţiştilor*,²⁴ *Combaterea catehismului bapţiştilor*,²⁵ *Lupta bapţiştilor împotriva preoţimii române*,²⁶ *Credinţa şi botezul – lămuriri pentru bapţişti*.²⁷ From a study of these apologetic and pastoral books and brochures, it can be noticed the preference for using the term “sect” in reference to the recognized neo-protestant confessions, although Grigore Comşa had been working for a considerable time in the Ministry that had recognized those cults and granted them a new designation. Thus,

we can affirm there was a difference between the official, academic language and the doctrinal, apologetic and ecclesiastical language.

In his work “Confesiuni și secte” (1929),²⁸ Bishop Grigorie Leu Botoșăneanu includes in the “sect” category, the Neo-protestant confessions recognized through repeated ministerial decisions and through the Law of the Cults from 1928.²⁹ Such examples are numerous in that period, and only in extremely rare occasions, the Orthodox Church officials did refer to the Neo-protestant confession using the designation conferred to them by the Romanian State. This continuing use of the “sect” term regardless the new designation gained by the recognized Neo-protestant confessions demonstrated the pejorative and negative character of this term, used with predilection by the Orthodox Church with reference to these confessions.

Deacon P. I. David himself noted that “the terms ‘sect’ and ‘cult’ are quite scornful and seem to imply a rather negative judgment.”³⁰ Therefore, he suggests that “more neutral terms could be used instead, such as *new religious movements*, *new religious groups*.”³¹ Not in the least, the problem becomes more sensitive when it comes to distinguish between these sects of Christian origin and the churches, ecclesiastic communities or legitimate movements within the churches. This last distinction is very important. “Heresy” and “sect” are two words by which, in the course of its history, the Church has designated those who broke up with the right faith.³² Jean Francois Wayer noted: “The sect is the other. Nobody likes this label stuck by the society and the *official* church to the minority religious groups, against their will. Having a clearly pejorative connotation, the designation of ‘sect’ has always been a means to exclude some faiths from the *respectable* religious paths category, as *sect* reminds of doctrinal absurdity, of fanaticism, of interdictions, of sectarianism.”³³

4) Neo-Protestant Confessions and Their Use of the Concept of “Sect”

With reference to the Baptist, Adventist and Plymouth Brethren confessions during the interwar period, the historian Viorel Achim

states that “the three organizations were not religious sects³⁴ either doctrinally, or from the perspective of the Romanian legislation (the Law of the Cults, from 1929, the subsequent laws).”³⁵ Yet, after September 1940, the three denominations had become the target of systematic politics to limit the freedom of faith, intended to intimidate the believers and make them to relinquish their religion and join the Orthodox Church. Gradually, at administrative level, it took place an assimilation of the Baptist, Seventh-day Adventists and Plymouth Brethren with the religious “sects.”³⁶

The researches done in the State Archive didn’t find any documents created by these confessions and addressed to the State, in which they would have assumed the “sect” designation. Nor in the Neo-protestant archives dating from this period (1918–1944)³⁷, have any documents been found to prove that these confessions were designating themselves as “sects”. This fact indicates that in the period of 1918–1944, these confessions regarded the term as bearing a negative connotation that was not putting them in a favorable light within the society. Consequently, they sought to avoid and get rid of this label.

Moreover, in the Annual Report from 1997, the UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Religion makes very clear his position with regard to the broad application of the concept of “religion” and the necessity of an equal treatment for all religions, including the so-called “sects” or “cults”.

In the first place, the Rapporteur noted the inadequate character of labeling certain faith communities as “sects”:

The term “sect” seems to have a pejorative connotation. A sect is considered to be different from a religion, and thus not entitled to the same protection. This kind of approach is indicative of a propensity to lump things together, to discriminate and to exclude, which is hard to justify and harder still to excuse, so injurious is it to religious freedom.³⁸

The Rapporteur concluded: “All in all, the distinction between a religion and a sect is too contrived to be acceptable. A sect that goes beyond simple belief and appeals to a divinity or, at the very least,

to the supernatural, the transcendent, the absolute, or the sacred, enters into the religious sphere and should enjoy the protection afforded to religions.”

Hence, we can note in the present times a distancing and dissociation from the term and concept of “sect” precisely because of its negative connotation that it has received and with which it has been used over the time. Therefore, we are assisting at the transformation of a term, made possible by its evolution in the Romanian language, which itself has changed over the years, with some words acquiring new valences and ceasing to define the same things as a century before.

Conclusions

First, the “sect”, as form of religious organization, is defined by appealing to Max Weber and Ernst Troeltsch in relation to and by comparison with the mother-church. While the latter is a religious organization well-integrated in society, large-sized, impersonal and bureaucratized, with the majority of its members being born in it, the sect is a voluntary association that does not claim authority on the religious life and the conduit of the non-members and that stands in a tense relation with the overall society.

Second, the term “sect” has different purports, depending on which side of the Atlantic you are. Thus, in the United States, the term is understood strictly as a sociological concept, as it was used by Max Weber and Ernst Troeltsch. But, in the European colloquial language, “sect” has turned into a value judgment. Being used by the Christian churches in an apologetic and polemical way, to describe the heretical groups that segregate from the official Christianity, the term has acquired in the last century, a negative and derogatory connotation, thus losing its original meaning. In the colloquial language, the negative meaning of the term prevails, while the sociological meaning is totally ignored. The negative highest point was reached during the totalitarian regimes.

Third, it can be incrementally noted that although an objective analysis of the sectarian phenomenon is attempted, there is in

these definitions, in a latent state, a strong deprecatory shade that will evolve with time, charging this idea of “sect” with negative connotations. This can be seen in the language used in the interwar era by the Orthodox Church, who conferred the designation of “sect” to the Adventist and Baptist confessions, although they had been recognized by the State as religious associations, with the exception of the Antonescu dictatorship, when they were outlawed.

Last but not least, currently, it can be noted a distancing from this term both in the State official papers and the traditional churches language, and an attempt to avoid the use of this term, as the State, and more recently, the church, too, become aware that we live in a world with democratic values and freedom of speech and faith.

NOTES

¹ Victor Neumann, *Este utilă rescrierea istoriei României? Evoluția conceptelor social-politice și alternativele interpretative în Istoria României prin Concepte* (București: Polirom, 2010), 29–30.

² *Ibid.*, 26–27.

³ Gheorghe Guțu, *Dicționar latin-român* (București: Humanitas, 2012), 456.

⁴ William H. Swatos Jr., ed. „Church–Sect Theory” in *Encyclopedia of Religion and Society*, (New York: Altamira Press, 1998), 90.

⁵ *Monitorul Oficial* nr. 282/29 martie 1923.

⁶ George Enache, “Problema sectelor în România. Din a doua jumătate a secolului al XIX-lea până în 1948” *Analele Universității ‘Dunărea de Jos’ Galați*, Seria 19, Istorie, vol. VI (2007): 106.

⁷ *Monitorul Oficial* nr. 282/29 martie 1923.

⁸ Enache, 106.

⁹ Bryan Wilson, *Religia din perspectivă sociologică* (București, 2000), 106–107.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 108–110.

¹¹ Enache, 107.

¹² *Apud* Jean–Francois Mayer, *Sectele. Nonconformisme creștine și noi religii* (București, 1998), 6.

¹³ Enache, 108.

¹⁴ Decizia Ministerială nr. 32 950/iunie 1921, as quoted by Dumitru Popa, *Pagini din Istoria Bisericii Adventiste de Ziua a Șaptea din România 1921–1936*, vol. II (București: Editura Viață și Sănătate, 2013), 48.

¹⁵ *Monitorul Oficial* nr. 31 din 10 februarie 1925. See also *Curierul misionar* nr. 3 (1925): 34–35; and A.N.D.J. Arad, fond Prefectura Județului Arad, Dosar nr. 6/1924, f.16–17.

¹⁶ ANIC, fond Ministerul Cultelor și Artelor, Direcția de Studii, dosar 1/1933, f.3.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ *Monitorul Oficial*, Partea I, nr. 305, 30 decembrie (1942): 11231–11232.

¹⁹ See Viorel Achim, "Situția sectelor religioase în Provincia Bucovina. Un studiu al Inspectoratului Regional de Poliție Cernăuți din septembrie 1943," in *Archiva Moldaviae*, vol. VI (2014): 351–427.

²⁰ According to the *Dictionary of the Romanian Theologians*, Grigore Comșa (or Gheorghe Comșa) was born on May 13, 1889, in Comana de Sus, Făgăraș (Brașov County), died on May 25, 1935, Arad. He attended the Lyceum in Făgăraș (1900–1908), the Theological Institute in Sibiu (1908–1911), the School of Law, University of Budapest (1911–1915), from which he received also his Doctor's degree. In parallel, he studied theology at the Catholic College of Theology in Budapest; afterwards he received his MA degree (1921), then the Doctor's degree (1925) at the College of Theology in Bucharest. He serves as deacon in Sibiu (1915), editor at *Telegraful Român* (1918), sub-director and general sub-director at the Ministry of Cults and Arts in Bucharest (1920–1925), at the same time—deacon at Amza Church, deputy in the first Parliament of the Unified Romania (1920). On May 3, 1925, he was elected Bishop of Arad, tonsured at Sinaia, receiving his monastic name of Grigorie, ordained as bishop on June 14, installed on July 12, 1925. He was honorary member of the Romania Academy (1934), of the Society of the Romanian Writers and of the Syndicate of the Journalists in Banat, member of the Astra Central Committee. Esteemed oratory and missionary bishop, he was a fervent defender of the Orthodox faith against the religious proselytism; he founded a number of theological collections (The Library of the Orthodox priest, The Library of the Orthodox believer). He coordinated the activity of the Theological Academy in Arad, of the Official Bulletin "The Church and the School" and the whole church life in the diocese. He published over 75 works (sermons, anti-sectarian brochures etc.)

²¹ Grigore Comșa, *Călăuza cunoașterii și combaterii sectelor*, București: Tipografia Bisericească, Cernica, 1926.

²² Grigore Comșa, *Pentru neam și lege*, București: Editura Librăriei Diecezane, 1923.

²³ Grigore Comșa, *Baptismul din punct de vedere istoric, național și religios*, Arad: Tiparul Tipografiei Diecezane, 1927.

²⁴ Grigore Comșa, *Cenușa de pe capul bapțiștilor*, Arad: Tiparul Tipografiei Diecezane, 1931.

²⁵ Grigore Comșa, *Combaterea catehismului bapțiștilor*, Arad: Tiparul Tipografiei Diecezane, 1926.

²⁶ Grigore Comșa, *Lupta bapțiștilor împotriva preoțimii române*, Arad: Tiparul Tipografiei Diecezane, 1925.

²⁷ Grigore Comșa, *Credința și botezul – lămuriri pentru bapțiști*, Arad: Tiparul Tipografiei Diecezane, 1926.

²⁸ Grigorie Leu Botoșăneanu, *Confesiuni și secte. Studiu istoric-misionar*, București: Tiparul Cărților Bisericești, 1929.

²⁹ Ibid., 41.

³⁰ P.I. David, *Călăuză Creștină. Sectologie. Pentru cunoașterea și apărarea dreptei credinței în fața prozelitismului sectant* (Curtea de Argeș: Editura Episcopiei Argeșului, 1994), 11.

³¹ Ibid.

³² “In theological language, ‘heresy’ designates both the erroneous teaching that caused the breaking up with church of a group of believers, and the group as such, while ‘sect’ designates only the group in itself. In Romanian, especially in the contemporary language, the term ‘heresy’ is used to designate the wrong teaching upheld and disseminated by a sect.” Cf. editor *Biserica și sectele* (București: Asociația Sf. Grigorie Palama, 1992), 18.

³³ Jean-Francois Wayer, *Sectele*, translated by Ruxana Pitea (București: Editura Enciclopedică, 1998), 5.

³⁴ Here he was referring to the Neo-protestant confessions officially recognized by the Romanian state, that is the Baptist, the Adventist and the Plymouth Brethren confession.

³⁵ Viorel Achim, “Situția ‘sectelor religioase’ în Provincia Bucovina. Un studiu al Inspectoratului Regional de Poliție Cernăuți din septembrie 1943 în *Archiva Moldaviae*, vol. VI (2014): 351.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 351–352.

³⁷ I have made researches in the archives of the Seventh-day Adventist, Baptist and Plymouth Brethren confessions.

³⁸ <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/G97/100/15/PDF/G9710015.pdf?OpenElement> (Last accessed May 2 2016).